

Reassessing Dependency Dynamics: Colonialism's Enduring Influence on Global Economic Structures

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Abstract:

Colonial powers have asserted political control, economical supremacy, and cultural hegemony over colonized regions, resulting in long-term inequalities and dependencies. Colonialism is a historical and enduring phenomenon, has profoundly shaped global socio-political and economic structures. Even post-colonialism, exploitation of third world countries persists unabated. New iterations of neocolonialism and cultural imperialism have evolved to sustain this exploitation. Dependency theory in globalization looks at how poorer countries rely on richer ones and international financial organizations. It criticizes how this creates unequal power and economic relationships. It says these dependencies stop countries from being economically independent and keep global inequalities going.

Keywords:

Colonial, economic and cultural hegemony, structural reforms, third world, exploitation, dominance, global north, global south.

Tracking the Roots of Colonialism:

Colonialism is a process whereby a foreign power or country (colonizer) usurps the governance and administrative control of another nation (colonized) for purposes of economic exploitation and cultural dominance. Colonialism has been a significant aspect of global history since antiquity. The modern epoch of colonialism commenced approximately in the 15th century, when European powers identified and exploited maritime routes, thereby instigating the subjugation and colonialization of territories

across Asia, Africa, North America, South America, Australia etc. Colonialism results in control over life of natives in political, economic, cultural, and social spheres.

In brief, colonialism is a practice in which the citizens of a sovereign nation, with the authorization, assistance, and backing of their government, migrate to an underdeveloped country to assert their dominance and establish governance- essentially subjugating it. There exists a fundamental similarity between colonialism and capitalism. In capitalism, one class exert dominance over another, whereas in colonialism, one nation asserts its supremacy over another. Today capitalism continues to perpetuate white supremacy, patriarchy, colonialism, imperialism, and other forms of oppression. It also perpetuates a global division of labor. For instance, nations within the Global South are abundant in resources; however, the impoverished populace lacks control over the wealth generated from these asserts. Instead, they are frequently compelled to migrate in search of employment in more affluent nations. The perpetuation of domestic labor as either unpaid or undercompensated has been integral to this system of capital accumulation. In this way, Capitalism and Colonialism exhibit profound similarities in their underlying mechanisms and consequences. Both paradigms are fundamentally predicted on exploitation, drawing upon the extraction of resources and labor from marginalized populations. Economic expansion lies at the heart of capitalism, propelling nations to pursue new markets and avenues for profit; conversely, colonialism entails territorial aggrandizement to secure resources and establish trade routes. This dynamic frequently engenders substantial social and economic disparities, concentrating wealth and power within a select few while systematically disenfranchising broader segments of society. Furthermore, colonialism can generate new markets for capitalist economies, facilitating a trade network that predominantly advantages the colonizers. Cultural hegemony emerges as another salient parallel, as both systems impose their respective values—capitalism through the proliferation of consumer culture and colonialism via the dominance of the colonizer's culture. Ultimately, both frameworks rationalize their practices through ideologies that frame exploitation as a vehicle for progress or benefit, underscoring the intricate entanglement of economic systems and imperial ambitions in shaping global dynamics and historical narratives.

Drawing on critical political economy, imperial social and economic history, and postcolonial theory, the concept of "colonial capitalism" encapsulates the complex and globally interconnected property structures, exchange systems, and labor regimes that underpinned Britain's imperial economy. In this context, it foregrounds the "dilemmas of liberalism" that emerged as Britain grappled with reconciling its self-image as a peaceful and commercial nation with the coercive economic practices it employed in its imperial territories. This tension underscores the inherent contradictions within liberal ideology, wherein the pursuit of profit and the expansion of markets often entailed the subjugation and exploitation of colonized peoples, thereby revealing the multifaceted nature of imperialism as both a catalyst for economic growth and a source of moral dissonance. Colonialism and Imperialism are interconnected concepts that both involve the extension of power and influence by one nation over another. Imperialism is the mother concept of colonialism and it is the ideology behind colonialism. Imperialism is a broader policy of extending a nation's power and influence through diplomacy or military force, while colonialism specifically involves the establishment of settlements and direct control over a foreign territory.

Colonialism and its Types:

Nancy Shoemaker is professor of history at the University of Connecticut. She described the twelve types of colonialism that are as follow: -

1. Settler Colonialism: -

In settler colonialism, a substantial influx of settlers seizes land and establishes themselves as the dominant demographic. As articulated by Patrick Wolfe in the *American Historical Review*, they employ a "logic of elimination" designed to systematically erase the original inhabitants from the landscape, relegating their existence to mere nostalgia. This strategy not only dispossesses indigenous peoples but also seeks to obliterate their cultural and historical presence, leaving behind a sanitized narrative that prioritizes the settler's claims and experiences.

2. Planter Colonialism: -

In planter colonialism, colonizers establish mass production of a single cash crop, such as sugar, coffee, or cotton. Although they represent a minority, the ruling class typically aligns with an imperial framework that grants them political, legal, and administrative authority. Unable to meet their labor needs with the indigenous population, they resort to importing African slaves or indentured laborers, exemplified by practices like the “coolie” and “blackbirding” trades. This system underscores the exploitative nature of colonial economies, prioritizing profit over the well-being of both native and imported labor forces.

3. Extractive Colonialism: -

All the colonizers want is a raw material found in a particular locate: beaver fur, buffalo hides, gold, guano, sandalwood. the desire for natural history specimens and ethnographic artifacts could also be considered extractive colonialism. A slash-and-burn operation, extractive colonialism does not necessarily entail permanent occupation, but it often seems to follow. Extractive colonizers might destroy or push away indigenous inhabitants to access resources but more typically depend upon native diplomatic mediation, environmental knowledge, and labor. Consequently, marriage " in the custom of the country" is more common with extractive colonialism than with settler and planter colonialism.

4. Trade Colonialism: -

Trade colonialism centers on the dominance of trading relationships, wherein the colonial power extracts raw materials from the periphery to manufacture goods for resale. This system relies on stringent trade regulations and enforcement mechanisms that facilitate capital accumulation in the colonial center. The dynamics of this exploitation underscore the systematic subjugation of peripheral economies, ensuring that wealth and resources flow inexorably toward the colonizers while perpetuating dependency and underdevelopment in the colonized regions. Classic histories of the British North American colonies emphasize the dominance of mercantile capitalism in regulating trading relationships. The colonial periphery supplies the metropole with raw materials, which the metropole processes into manufactured goods such as firearms,

textiles, and other commodities for sale within its colonies. Tariffs and stringent enforcement against smuggling serve to regulate trade, ensuring that capital flows predominantly into the metropole.

Moreover, trade coercion extends beyond imperial frameworks; for instance, British concessions to open additional ports beyond Canton for foreign trade exemplify the aggressive tactics employed to expand economic control. This dynamic not only underscores the exploitative nature of colonial commerce but also reveals how imperial powers manipulate international trade networks to entrench their dominance, perpetuating a cycle of dependency and economic subjugation in the colonies.

5. Transport Colonialism: -

Transport colonialism is about establishing transportation infrastructure and hubs, impacting local economies and cultures. It involves creating supply depots, route defences, and engineering projects that facilitate travel and contact. In this way, Transport colonialism involves the strategic establishment of infrastructure to facilitate movement and trade, often under the guise of economic benefit. The U.S. pressure on Japan in 1854, spearheaded by Commodore Matthew Perry, exemplifies this; it aimed to secure safe ports for American whaling ships rather than merely expanding trade. This concept encompasses hubs like the Azores and Hawai'i, coaling stations for steamships, and military airstrips from World War II. It also includes protective fortifications along migration routes, such as those on the Oregon Trail, and major engineering projects like the Panama Canal. While transport colonialism may not directly displace native populations, it significantly alters local economies and cultures by creating new contact zones.

6. Imperial Power Colonialism: -

Imperial power colonialism involves expanding territories for the sake of supremacy or domination. It includes various forms like the Settler, Planter, and Extractive colonialism. Colonialism often serves multiple purposes, including territorial expansion, economic gain, and geopolitical competition. In 18th-century North America, the rivalry between France and Britain exemplified how imperial ambitions

fuelled settler and extractive colonialism. Similarly, in the Pacific, Tongan expansion under leaders like King George Tupou I and Ma'afu illustrated that imperial ambitions were not exclusive to European powers. This dynamic highlights the broader nature of imperialism, where various cultures engage in expansionist practices driven by the desire for influence and control.

7. Not-in-My-Backyard Colonialism: -

Not-in-My-Backyard colonialism involves the strategic use of remote, ostensibly empty territories for purposes deemed undesirable in the colonizers' homelands. This approach is exemplified by the British designation of Australia as terra nullius, facilitating its establishment as a penal colony at Botany Bay. Similarly, France and Chile utilized Pacific islands for their own penal colonies. In the 20th century, the United States relocated inhabitants from the Marshall Islands for atomic testing, echoing settler colonialism's dispossession but under the guise of scientific progress rather than settlement. France also employed this strategy, using Algeria and later the Tuamotus as sites for nuclear tests. This form of colonialism highlights a deliberate disregard for the sovereignty of marginalized populations in favor of exploiting distant lands for various controversial experiments and punitive measures.

8. Legal Colonialism: -

Legal colonialism is characterized by the imposition of legal authority over foreign territories through diplomatic means and military force. A prominent example of this practice is the United States' establishment of extraterritorial courts in the 19th century, particularly through treaties with nations deemed "barbaric." The 1844 Treaty of Wanghia is a key illustration, as it allowed U.S. consuls to administer extraterritorial courts, enabling American nationals to be tried under U.S. law instead of local jurisdictions. This legal framework not only asserted American dominance but also persisted into the 20th century with the establishment of the U.S. District Court of Shanghai, further entrenching American legal authority abroad and reflecting a broader pattern of legal imperialism.

9. Rogue Colonialism: -

Colonialism is not always a state-sanctioned enterprise. Rogue colonialism operates outside formal state endorsement, where Filibusters, private entities or individuals assert control over foreign territories. These actions often provoke later state intervention aimed at legitimizing and safeguarding such endeavors. The state may subsequently intervene to legitimize and annex the territorial claims of rogue colonizers, as exemplified by the United States' annexation of Texas in 1845 and Hawai'i in 1898. Alternatively, the state may publicly disavow and condemn the actions of its own citizens to avoid diplomatic repercussions, as seen in the US government's refusal to support William Walker's filibustering endeavors in Central America. Similarly, Britain disapproved of Edward Wakefield's New Zealand Company and utilized the 1840 Treaty of Waitangi to curb the activities of private land speculators. Rogue colonialism, motivated by other forms of colonialism such as settler colonialism or imperial power, raises crucial questions about the complex dynamics between individual actors and the state in the context of colonial pursuits, highlighting the tensions between private initiative and state oversight.

10. Missionary Colonialism: -

As private agents, missionaries could be considered rogue colonizers, but they deserve their own category for the distinctiveness of their purpose. They need native people to justify their existence. Missionary colonialism pertains to the confluence of religious missions, particularly Christian, with colonial expansionism. Missionaries endeavoured to convert indigenous populations, frequently culminating in the suppression of indigenous religions and cultural practices. They instituted educational and healthcare initiatives that, while occasionally advantageous, predominantly propagated Western ideologies. Numerous missionaries endorsed colonial authorities, operating under the presumption that colonial governance would "civilize" local communities. Indigenous responses were heterogeneous, oscillating between acquiescence and resistance, thereby engendering complex dynamics between missionary entities and local cultures. The legacy of this phenomenon remains ambivalent, profoundly influencing the religious, cultural, and social paradigms of formerly colonized societies.

11. Romantic Colonialism: -

Colonizers who seek different environments and cultures for escape fall under this category. Sometimes they hope native people will participate in the romantic fantasy, portraying local culture. Romantic Colonialism entails a form of escapism wherein colonizers seek to flee to environments and cultures that starkly contrast with their primary residences. This phenomenon is exemplified by Thor Heyerdahl's desire for isolation in the Marquesas, as expressed in his 1974 work *Fatu-Hiva*, where he sought to disconnect from the outside world. In contrast, romantic colonizers like Paul Gauguin and Robert Louis Stevenson, as well as consumers of mass tourism, often expect indigenous populations to participate in their romanticized fantasies, performing local customs and cultures for their benefit. This phenomenon is aptly captured in Matt Matsuda's 2005 work, "Empire of Love," which highlights how French colonization in the Pacific was fuelled by a desire for exoticism and romanticized notions of indigenous cultures. This form of colonialism perpetuates a complex power dynamic, where the colonizer's desire for escape and fantasy is predicated on the exploitation and commodification of native cultures.

12. Postcolonial Colonialism: -

Even after achieving independence, former colonies continue to grapple with the enduring legacy of colonialism. Economic dependencies, entrenched cultural ties, and systems imposed during colonial rule persist in multifaceted forms, hindering genuine autonomy and progress. Former colonies cannot so easily shake off the colonial legacy. Economic dependency and entanglements continue, as do bonds of affinity. Fiji, nearly 100 years a British planter colony and independent since 1970, continues to bear the imprint of its colonial past in its multiethnic, multilingual citizenry; its unusual British-imposed, aboriginal-protectionist landholding regime; and the popularity of rugby among its people.

Dependency Theory of Development:

Dependency theory, a prominent framework within the social sciences for elucidating the economic development of nation-states, emerged during the late 1950s

and evolved over the subsequent two decades, primarily through the intellectual contributions of Raul Prebisch and Hans Singer. This theoretical construct posits that the economic conditions of developing nations are fundamentally shaped by their exploitative relationships with more affluent countries, thereby perpetuating a cycle of dependency that hinders autonomous growth and sustainable development. They discerned that economic growth in advanced industrialized nations did not inherently translate into parallel growth in poorer countries. Indeed, their research indicated that economic activities in wealthier nations frequently precipitated significant economic challenges for the less developed regions. The persistence of poverty in these underdeveloped countries appeared to be closely tied to their role as exporters of primary commodities, which were then transformed into manufactured goods by affluent nations and resold to the poorer states. Marxist theorists, including André Gunder Frank, Paul A. Baran, and Paul Sweezy, contended that this enduring poverty was fundamentally a consequence of capitalist structures, which inherently perpetuate inequality and stifle genuine development. Three principal characteristics of dependency theory are notable. First, the international system is perceived as bifurcated into two distinct categories of states: dominant and dependent. Second, dependency theory posits that extrinsic factors are pivotal in shaping the economic dynamics of subordinate states. Third, the relationships, underpinned by entrenched historical patterns between hegemonic and subordinate states, constitute a dynamic process wherein interactions significantly contribute to the perpetuation of systemic inequalities.

Like Marx, American sociologist Immanuel Wallerstein predicted that capitalism will be replaced by a socialist economy. Wallerstein, a Marxist thinker analysed World order theory. Immanuel Wallerstein's World Systems Theory articulates a tripartite schema of the global economy, delineating core, semi-periphery, and periphery nations. Core nations, characterized by advanced development, robust economies, and technological pre-eminence, exert hegemony over global trade and political dynamics. In contrast, semi-periphery nations inhabit a liminal space, concurrently exploiting peripheral countries while themselves being subject to exploitation by core nations. Peripheral nations, marked by underdevelopment, serve as reservoirs of raw materials and inexpensive labor for core nations, yet they are bereft of

political clout and economic stability. Wallerstein's framework elucidates the intrinsic inequalities endemic to global capitalism, offering a profound critique of traditional linear developmental paradigms and underscoring the historical and systemic interrelations that govern these global stratifications.

Global North-South Divide: -

There are two distinct economic worlds that shape global dynamics: the Global North and the Global South. The Global South comprises nations frequently classified as developing, less developed, or underdeveloped, predominantly situated in Africa, Asia and Latin America. These countries grapple with elevated levels of poverty, significant income inequality, and difficult living conditions, starkly contrasting with the affluence of the Global North. The Global North, characterized by its wealth, encompasses primarily North America and Europe, with some inclusion of affluent regions in Oceania and beyond. This dichotomy underscores the systematic disparities in economic development and living standard between the two spheres, highlighting the challenges faced by Global South in achieving sustainable growth and social equity. The fundamental objective of any development program is to mitigate poverty, thereby facilitating improved living conditions for the populace. Development acts as a remedy for poverty, as a society beset by poverty cannot be deemed developed. Consequently, poverty embodies the essence of underdevelopment, while development signifies the near-total absence of poverty.

If we equate poverty with underdevelopment, and development with the absence of poverty, we can delineate the global landscape into two predominant economic spheres: the developed nations of Europe and the underdeveloped nations of the Global South. Historically, these underdeveloped societies have been labelled as Third World or Less Developed Countries, a classification that predominantly encompasses nations in Africa, Asia, and Latin America. These countries are characterized by markedly low levels of economic and political development, a propensity to resist the hegemonic influences of capitalism, and a colonial legacy that has profoundly influenced their trajectories post-independence. The impetus for self-determination gained significant momentum after 1945, in the wake of the Second World War, as numerous Third World

countries endeavoured to achieve independence and assert their sovereignty on the global stage. By 1945, post-World War II, scholarly interest in development surged as formerly colonized societies gained independence. The stark inequalities created by colonialism—resulting in wealth for some and poverty for others—led to the development of concepts like “underdeveloped” and “developed”, “metropole” and “satellite”, and “centre” and “periphery” for classifying economic advancement. The Global North signifies developed economies, while the Global South denotes underdeveloped ones. Key indicators distinguishing these groups include political stability, technological capability, wealth distribution, and demographic trends.

A Way Forward: -

To bridge the North–South research divide and advance the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), it's crucial to strengthen the scientific and technological capacities of Southern countries, support their research and innovation with good policies, improve education, and enhance cooperation between regions. Practical steps are needed from various actors, including intergovernmental organizations, international donors, and Northern institutions. For example, programs like the IPCC Scholarship and PROVIA Fellowship are helping to build research capacities in Southern countries, and the Wellcome Trust is supporting early-career scientists from non-G7 countries to promote global research collaboration. Reform international institutions to better represent and serve the interests of developing countries, ensuring that they have a voice in global economic decisions. Move away from exploitative practices towards equitable partnerships. This includes fair trade agreements and supportive policies that help developing countries build their own economic capabilities.

Vladimir Lenin's economic development approach focused on transitioning from capitalism to socialism through nationalization of industries and banks, central economic planning, and collectivization of agriculture. He promoted worker control of production, rapid industrialization to build economic strength, and redistribution of wealth to reduce inequality. These strategies aimed to create a state-controlled economy that would eliminate private ownership and align production with socialist goals.

To address the global North-South divide and its colonial legacies, a robust approach is needed. This includes reforming trade and investment practices to ensure fair access for Southern countries, cancelling or restructuring their debt to alleviate economic burdens, and investing in education and technology to enhance their capabilities. Reforming global governance to give Southern nations a stronger voice in international institutions is crucial. Additionally, supporting the development of local industries in the Global South can reduce reliance on Northern imports and aid. These measures are essential for creating a more equitable global economic system and mitigating the long-term effects of colonialism.

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